

Filiform Lie algebras with low derived length

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Abstract

We construct, for any $n \geq 5$, a family of complex filiform Lie algebras with derived length at most 3 and dimension n . We also give examples of n -dimensional filiform Lie algebras with derived length greater than 3.

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1 Introduction

The derived length, also known as solvability index, of nilpotent groups or nilpotent Lie algebras has been studied by a number of authors. In the case of finite p -groups this study was initiated by Burnside [11, 12] and then continued by several authors (e.g. Philip Hall [22], Magnus [27], Itô [24], Hall-Higman [23], Blackburn [4], Mann [28] among many others). In the case of a nilpotent Lie algebra, the study of its derived length has been treated in several papers, e.g. by Dixmier [15], Patterson [31, 32], Bokut [5]. In [6] the authors show that there are filiform Lie algebras of arbitrary derived length. They describe, for any $k \geq 2$, a filiform Lie algebra of derived length k and dimension n for each n satisfying $2^k \leq n + 1 < 2^{k+1}$. These algebras were studied by Benoist in [3].

In this paper we construct, for any $n \geq 5$, a family of complex filiform Lie algebras with derived length at most 3 and dimension n , see Theorem 3. To this end we improve the result [14, Prop. 2] and describe the law of any filiform Lie algebra of dimension $n \geq 5$ with respect to a suitable adapted basis by using two numerical invariants associated with the algebra, see Theorem 2. This result is related to the description of the affine variety of n -dimensional filiform Lie algebras given in [29, Sec. 4], where the variety of Lie algebras of maximal class is described. See also [34] where the related notion of narrow Lie algebras is treated.

Theorem 2 generalizes a result of Bratzlavsky [7] valid for metabelian Lie algebras. We also construct a family of complex filiform Lie algebras of dimension 15 and derived length 4 generalising the one given by [8, Ex. 3.2]. Let us remark that there is no complex filiform Lie algebra of dimension less than or equal to 14 and derived length 4 (see [8, Prop. 3.7]).

If the derived length of a solvable Lie algebra is k one also says that the algebra is k -step solvable, see Definition 2. Solvable Lie algebras with low derived length have been previously

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studied in several papers. For example, 1-step solvable Lie algebras are the abelian ones. Abelian subalgebras and ideals are very useful in the study of Lie algebra contractions and degenerations. There is extensive literature on these topics, in particular for low-dimensional Lie algebras, as can be seen in [10, 19, 21] and the references given therein.

Next, 2-step solvable Lie algebras are called metabelian. These algebras have been studied in [1] by using the notion of weight graphs. Moreover, they admit abelian complex and Novikov structures, see [2, 9]. In [35] the author uses 3-step solvable Lie algebras to construct a homogeneous conformally parallel Spin(7) metric on a certain solvmanifold. Finally, it is proved in [30] that 3-step solvable Lie algebras contain the first oscillator algebras with non-trivial semi-equicontinuous coadjoint orbits.

2 Preliminaries

In this section we recall some preliminary concepts, results and notations on Lie algebras. We have mainly followed [20, 25, 33, 36]. From here on, only finite-dimensional Lie algebras over the field of complex numbers are considered. Given a Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} , a vector subspace \mathfrak{h} of \mathfrak{g} is an *ideal* if $[\mathfrak{h}, \mathfrak{g}] \subseteq \mathfrak{h}$. We denote by $\dim \mathfrak{h}$ the dimension of \mathfrak{h} as a vector space.

The *descendant central series* of ideals, also known as the *lower central series*, of a given Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} is the filtration

$$C^1 \mathfrak{g} \supseteq C^2 \mathfrak{g} \supseteq \dots \supseteq C^k \mathfrak{g} \supseteq \dots$$

where

$$C^1 \mathfrak{g} = \mathfrak{g} \text{ and } C^k \mathfrak{g} = [C^{k-1} \mathfrak{g}, \mathfrak{g}] \text{ for all } k \geq 2.$$

One has $[C^k \mathfrak{g}, C^\ell \mathfrak{g}] \subseteq C^{k+\ell} \mathfrak{g}$ for all $k, \ell \geq 1$.

Definition 1. A Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} is said to be *nilpotent* if there exists $m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $C^m \mathfrak{g} = \{0\}$. The smallest such m is called the *nilpotency class* (or the *nilindex*) of \mathfrak{g} .

The *derived series* of ideals of a given Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} is the filtration

$$D^0 \mathfrak{g} \supseteq D^1 \mathfrak{g} \supseteq \dots \supseteq D^k \mathfrak{g} \supseteq \dots$$

where

$$D^0 \mathfrak{g} = \mathfrak{g} \text{ and } D^k \mathfrak{g} = [D^{k-1} \mathfrak{g}, D^{k-1} \mathfrak{g}] \text{ for all } k \geq 1.$$

Definition 2. A Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} is said to be *solvable* if there exists $m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $D^m \mathfrak{g} = \{0\}$. The smallest such m is called the *derived length* (or the *solubility index*, or even the *solvindex*) of \mathfrak{g} . We say that \mathfrak{g} is *m-step solvable* if the derived length of \mathfrak{g} is m .

The derived Lie algebra of \mathfrak{g} is by definition $C^2 \mathfrak{g} = D^1 \mathfrak{g} = [\mathfrak{g}, \mathfrak{g}]$. From here on, we will denote the derived algebra by $D\mathfrak{g}$. A Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} satisfying $D\mathfrak{g} = \{0\}$ is called *abelian*. If $D\mathfrak{g}$ is abelian, i.e. if $D^2 \mathfrak{g} = \{0\}$, then \mathfrak{g} is said to be *metabelian*.

Let us notice that every nilpotent Lie algebra is solvable, since $D^{k-1}\mathfrak{g} \subseteq C^k\mathfrak{g}$ for all $k \geq 1$. Moreover, we have $D^k\mathfrak{g} \subset C^{2^k}\mathfrak{g}$, see e.g. [25, page 25]. This means in particular that if $\dim \mathfrak{g} \leq 2^k$, for some integer k , then the derived length of \mathfrak{g} is less than or equal to k .

Definition 3. [37, Section 1.5] A n -dimensional Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} is said to be *filiform* if its descendant central series satisfies

$$\dim(C^k\mathfrak{g}) = n - k \text{ for all } 2 \leq k \leq n. \quad (1)$$

Any n -dimensional filiform Lie algebra is nilpotent and its nilpotency class is n .

A basis $\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ of a filiform Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} is called *adapted*, see [37, Sec. 4.2], if the following relations² hold

$$\begin{aligned} [e_1, e_h] &= e_{h-1} & \text{for } 3 \leq h \leq n, \\ [e_2, e_h] &= 0 & \text{for } 1 \leq h \leq n, \\ [e_3, e_h] &= 0 & \text{for } 2 \leq h \leq n. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

As it was pointed out in [37, Section 4.2] any filiform Lie algebra admits an adapted basis. In fact, with respect to an adapted basis, the ideals of the descendant central series are given by

$$C^k\mathfrak{g} = \langle e_2, \dots, e_{n-k+1} \rangle \quad (3)$$

where the angle brackets mean the \mathbb{C} -vector space generated by the corresponding vectors.

A n -dimensional filiform Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} is called a *model* filiform Lie algebra (see [20]) if the only nonzero brackets in its law are $[e_1, e_h] = e_{h-1}$, for $3 \leq h \leq n$, where $\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ is an adapted basis of \mathfrak{g} . This condition is obviously independent of the chosen adapted basis in \mathfrak{g} . Notice that for $n \leq 4$ every filiform Lie algebra is a model filiform Lie algebra.

2.1 Two Numerical Invariants of Filiform Lie Algebras

We recall the definition of two invariants of a filiform Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} introduced in [16]. These invariants are defined for non-model filiform Lie algebras, so we can assume that $n > 4$. First, the invariant $z_1 = z_1(\mathfrak{g})$ is defined as

$$z_1 = \max\{k \in \mathbb{N} \mid C_{\mathfrak{g}}(C^{n-k+2}\mathfrak{g}) \supseteq C^2\mathfrak{g}\}$$

where $C_{\mathfrak{g}}(\mathfrak{h})$ is the centralizer of a given Lie subalgebra \mathfrak{h} of \mathfrak{g} , i.e. the set of elements in \mathfrak{g} whose bracket with any element of \mathfrak{h} is zero.

The invariant $z_2 = z_2(\mathfrak{g})$ is defined as $z_2 = \max\{k \in \mathbb{N} \mid C^{n-k+1}\mathfrak{g} \text{ is abelian}\}$. Consequently, $C^{n-z_2+1}\mathfrak{g}$ is the largest abelian ideal in the lower central series of \mathfrak{g} .

Remark 1. Notice that, for any n -dimensional non-model filiform Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} , one has $z_2(\mathfrak{g}) \leq n - 1$. Moreover, $z_2(\mathfrak{g}) = n - 1$ if and only if \mathfrak{g} is metabelian.

²To simplify notations, the definition we give here is slightly different from, although equivalent to, the original one given in [37, Sec. 4.2].

Equivalent definitions for the invariants z_1 and z_2 , more appropriate for practical use, are: $z_1 = \min \{k \geq 4 \mid [e_k, e_n] \neq 0\}$ and $z_2 = \min \{k \geq 4 \mid [e_k, e_{k+1}] \neq 0\}$, where $\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ is an adapted basis of \mathfrak{g} .

These two invariants satisfy the following inequalities, see [16, Th. 15]:

$$4 \leq z_1 \leq z_2 < n \leq 2z_2 - 2. \quad (4)$$

Given a n -dimensional non-model filiform Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} , we use the triple (z_1, z_2, n) to summarize the information about both invariants and the dimension of \mathfrak{g} .

2.2 Previous results

In [7, Lemme 1] Bratzlavsky obtained the general law for a filiform metabelian Lie algebra, that is, a filiform Lie algebra associated with the triple $(z_1, n-1, n)$, for $4 \leq z_1 \leq n-1$. In [26, Sec. 1] the author improves, for the infinite dimensional case, the classification result of [7, Prop. 3] only valid in finite dimension. On the other hand, in [18, Lemma 1.2] the authors give the parametric expression of a list of basic brackets for any n -dimensional filiform Lie algebra.

Theorem 1. [7, Lemme 1] *Let \mathfrak{g} be a filiform Lie algebra of dimension $n \geq 5$ whose derived Lie algebra $D\mathfrak{g}$ is abelian. Then there exist a basis $\{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$ of \mathfrak{g} and some complex numbers $\lambda_0, \dots, \lambda_{n-5}$ such that*

$$[x_1, x_i] = x_{i+1} \text{ for } 2 \leq i \leq n-1; \quad [x_i, x_j] = 0 \text{ for } 3 \leq i < j \leq n \quad \text{and}$$

$$[x_2, x_i] = \sum_{r=0}^{n-i-2} \lambda_r x_{i+2+r} \text{ for } 3 \leq i \leq n-2.$$

Notice that when $\lambda_0 = \dots = \lambda_{n-5} = 0$, we obtain the model filiform Lie algebra since the equalities $e_1 = x_1, e_2 = x_n, e_3 = x_{n-1}, \dots, e_n = x_2$ define an adapted basis of \mathfrak{g} .

Notation 1. *Given a n -dimensional Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} with basis $\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ and an integer $1 \leq h \leq n$ we denote by $P_h : \mathfrak{g} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ the \mathbb{C} -linear map defined as follows: for any vector $u \in \mathfrak{g}$, $P_h(u)$ is the coordinate of u with respect to the basis vector e_h , i.e.*

$$u = \sum_{h=1}^n P_h(u) e_h.$$

The following theorem is stated in [13, Prop. 2] but we correct here a mistake there on the coefficient of e_2 in the brackets $[e_{z_1+k}, e_{z_2+\ell}]$. More precisely, next theorem describes the law of any filiform non-model Lie algebra, with associated triple (z_1, z_2, n) with respect to a suitable adapted basis. This result can be compared to the description of the affine variety of n -dimensional filiform Lie algebras given in [29, Sec. 4].

Theorem 2. [13, Prop. 2] *Let \mathfrak{g} be a n -dimensional non-model filiform Lie algebra with associated triple (z_1, z_2, n) . Then, there exist an adapted basis $\{e_1, \dots, e_n\}$ of \mathfrak{g} and some complex numbers α_i , γ_j and β_{kl} , with $1 \leq i \leq z_2 - z_1 + 1$, $1 \leq j \leq 2n - z_1 - z_2 - 2$, $2 \leq \ell \leq n - z_2$, and $1 \leq k < z_2 - z_1 + \ell$, such that*

$$\begin{aligned} [e_1, e_h] &= e_{h-1} \quad \text{for } 3 \leq h \leq n, \\ [e_{z_1+i}, e_{z_2+1}] &= \alpha_1 e_{i+2} + \alpha_2 e_{i+1} + \dots + \alpha_{i+1} e_2 \quad \text{for } 0 \leq i \leq z_2 - z_1, \\ [e_{z_1}, e_{z_2+j}] &= \alpha_1 e_{j+1} + \gamma_1 e_j + \dots + \gamma_{j-1} e_2 \quad \text{for } 2 \leq j \leq n - z_2, \\ [e_{z_1+k}, e_{z_2+\ell}] &= \sum_{h=2}^{k+\ell} P_h ([e_{z_1+k-1}, e_{z_2+\ell}] + [e_{z_1+k}, e_{z_2+\ell-1}]) e_{h+1} + \beta_{k\ell} e_2, \\ &\quad \text{for } 2 \leq \ell \leq n - z_2, \quad 1 \leq k < z_2 - z_1 + \ell. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. The proof of this Theorem follows the one of [13, Prop. 2] bearing in mind that at the end of that proof, the coefficient of e_2 in the bracket $[e_{z_1+k}, e_{z_2+\ell}]$ is in general different from the coefficients $\{\alpha_i\}$ and $\{\gamma_j\}$. □

Remark 2. *Notice first that when all the parameters in Theorem 2 equal 0, i.e. $\alpha_i = \gamma_j = \beta_{kl} = 0$, we obtain the model filiform Lie algebra of dimension n .*

Notice also that the Jacobi identity induces quadratic relations among the parameters α_i , β_{kl} and γ_j . These quadratic relations define a certain non-empty Zariski closed set Z in the affine space \mathbb{C}^μ of the parameters. Here the number of parameters is given by

$$\mu = (z_2 - z_1 + 1) + (n - z_2 - 1) + \frac{(n - z_2 - 1)(n + z_2 - 2z_1)}{2} = \frac{(n - z_2)(n + z_2 - 2z_1 + 1)}{2}.$$

Moreover, the Lie algebras in Theorem 2 must be non-model and with numerical invariants (z_1, z_2, n) . These last conditions define a certain Zariski open set of the previous closed set Z .

Notation 2. *The parametric family of filiform Lie algebras described in Theorem 2 is denoted by $\mathcal{F}_{\alpha\beta\gamma}$. Notice that, by definition, the Lie algebras in this family have a fixed associated triple (z_1, z_2, n) . In order to simplify notations, we drop this dependency in the notation $\mathcal{F}_{\alpha\beta\gamma}$. According to Theorem 2, the set of laws of n -dimensional non-model filiform Lie algebras is the disjoint union of the sets $\mathcal{F}_{\alpha\beta\gamma}$ when (z_1, z_2, n) varies in the index set defined by inequalities (4); that is, when $4 \leq z_1 \leq z_2 < n \leq 2z_2 - 2$.*

Remark 3. *We will see in the proof of Theorem 3 that if (z_1, z_2, n) satisfies*

$$4 \leq z_1 \leq 2(n - z_2) - 4 \quad \text{and} \quad z_1 \leq z_2 \leq n - 3 \leq 2z_2 - 5,$$

then $\mathcal{F}_{\alpha\beta\gamma}$ is the empty set, see Remark 5.

Let us notice that Theorem 2 implies Theorem 1 for non-model filiform Lie algebras.

Remark 4. According to Notation 1 and Theorem 2 the linear maps P_h satisfy the following relation

$$P_h([e_i, e_j]) = P_{h-1}([e_{i-1}, e_j] + [e_i, e_{j-1}]) \quad \text{for } 1 < i < j \leq n.$$

This will be used in the next section.

3 Main results

This section contains the main new results of this work. We state four Lemmas that are used to prove that the derived length of a family of finite dimensional filiform Lie algebra is at most 3 (see Theorem 3). This family will be defined in Notation 5.

We start with Lemma 1 in order to study the case where $z_2 = n - 2$.

Lemma 1. Let \mathfrak{g} be a n -dimensional non-model filiform Lie algebra with $z_2 = n - 2$. Then $n \geq 6$ and \mathfrak{g} has derived length 3.

Proof. First, the condition $n \geq 6$ follows from the fact that \mathfrak{g} is a non-model filiform Lie algebra and from inequalities (4). Moreover, $D^2\mathfrak{g}$ is nonzero since $z_2 = n - 2$ (see Remark 1). According to Theorem 2, we have the following general law for the algebra \mathfrak{g} , with respect to a suitable adapted basis

$$\begin{aligned} [e_1, e_h] &= e_{h-1}, \quad 3 \leq h \leq n, \\ [e_{z_1+i}, e_{n-1}] &= \alpha_1 e_{i+2} + \alpha_2 e_{i+1} + \cdots + \alpha_{i+1} e_2, \quad 0 \leq i \leq n - z_1 - 2, \\ [e_{z_1}, e_n] &= \alpha_1 e_3 + \gamma_1 e_2, \\ [e_{z_1+k}, e_n] &= \sum_{h=2}^{k+2} P_h([e_{z_1+k-1}, e_n] + [e_{z_1+k}, e_{n-1}])e_{h+1} + \beta_{k2} e_2, \quad 0 < k < n - z_1. \end{aligned}$$

According to equality (3), $D^2\mathfrak{g} \subseteq \langle e_2, \dots, e_{n-z_1} \rangle$ is abelian since $n - z_1 < n - 1$ and then $D^3\mathfrak{g} = \{0\}$. \square

Notation 3. We will use the following notations

$$p = 2n - z_1 - 2z_2 - 3 \qquad q = n - z_2 - 2 \qquad r = n - z_1 - 1$$

$$R_k = \left(\binom{r}{k} - \binom{r}{k-1} \right) \binom{q}{k} \quad S_k = \left(\binom{r}{k} - \binom{r}{k-1} \right) \binom{q}{k-1}.$$

Given a real number y the expression $[y]$ denotes the largest integer less than or equal to y .

For the next three Lemmas, we will refer to the coefficients $\alpha_i, \beta_{k\ell}, \gamma_j$ introduced in Theorem 2. If no confusion arises we use $\beta_{k,\ell}$ instead of $\beta_{k\ell}$. Moreover, in the proofs of Lemmas 2 and 3, we will use the following property that was proved in [17, Lemma 4]:

$$[e_i, e_j] = 0 \quad \text{for } 1 < i < z_1, \quad j > 1.$$

Lemma 2. [13, Prop. 6] *Let \mathfrak{g} be a n -dimensional non-model filiform Lie algebra. If the derived algebra $\mathcal{D}\mathfrak{g}$ is not abelian, then $\alpha_1 = 0$.*

Proof. We give here an alternative proof to the one in [13, Prop. 6], which is related to other results of this section.

We assume that \mathfrak{g} is a non-model filiform Lie algebra with associated triple (z_1, z_2, n) . Let us consider the Jacobi identity

$$J(e_{z_1}, e_{n-1}, e_n) = [[e_{z_1}, e_{n-1}], e_n] + [[e_{n-1}, e_n], e_{z_1}] + [[e_n, e_{z_1}], e_{n-1}] = 0.$$

Notice first that by Theorem 2,

$$[e_{z_1}, e_{n-1}] = \alpha_1 e_{n-z_2} + \gamma_1 e_{n-z_2-1} + \cdots + \gamma_{n-z_2-2} e_2$$

and then we have that the first term of the Jacobi identity is given by

$$\begin{aligned} [[e_{z_1}, e_{n-1}], e_n] &= \alpha_1 [e_{n-z_2}, e_n] + \gamma_1 [e_{n-z_2-1}, e_n] + \cdots + \gamma_{n-z_2-2} [e_2, e_n] = \\ &= \alpha_1 [e_{n-z_2}, e_n] + \gamma_1 [e_{n-z_2-1}, e_n] + \cdots + \gamma_{n-z_2-2} [e_{z_1}, e_n]. \end{aligned}$$

Next, for the second term, we have

$$[e_{n-1}, e_n] = \sum_{h=2}^{q+r+2} P_h([e_{n-2}, e_n]) e_{h+1} + \beta_{n-1-z_1, n-z_2} e_2,$$

so

$$\begin{aligned} [e_{z_1}, [e_{n-1}, e_n]] &= \sum_{h=2}^{q+r+2} P_h([e_{n-2}, e_n]) [e_{z_1}, e_{h+1}] + \beta_{n-1-z_1, n-z_2} [e_{z_1}, e_2] \\ &= \sum_{h=z_1}^{q+r+2} P_h([e_{n-2}, e_n]) [e_{z_1}, e_{h+1}]. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, for the last term, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} [e_{z_1}, e_n] &= \alpha_1 e_{n-z_2+1} + \gamma_1 e_{n-z_2} + \cdots + \gamma_{n-z_2-1} e_2 \\ [[e_{z_1}, e_n], e_{n-1}] &= \alpha_1 [e_{n-z_2+1}, e_{n-1}] + \gamma_1 [e_{n-z_2}, e_{n-1}] + \cdots + \gamma_{n-z_2-1} [e_2, e_{n-1}] = \\ &= \alpha_1 [e_{n-z_2+1}, e_{n-1}] + \gamma_1 [e_{n-z_2}, e_{n-1}] + \cdots + \gamma_{n-z_1-z_2+1} [e_{z_1}, e_{n-1}]. \end{aligned}$$

Since $\mathcal{D}\mathfrak{g}$ is not abelian, at least, one of the three terms of the Jacobi identity is not trivially null. In this way, $J(e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-1}, e_n) = 0$ is equivalent to

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_1 [e_{n-z_2}, e_n] + \gamma_1 [e_{n-z_2-1}, e_n] + \cdots + \gamma_{n-z_2-z_1} [e_{z_1}, e_n] - \sum_{h=z_1}^{q+r+2} P_h([e_{n-2}, e_n]) [e_{z_1}, e_{h+1}] \\ - \alpha_1 [e_{n-z_2+1}, e_{n-1}] - \gamma_1 [e_{n-z_2}, e_{n-1}] - \cdots - \gamma_{n-z_1-z_2+1} [e_{z_1}, e_{n-1}] = 0. \end{aligned}$$

The coefficient of e_{p+4} in the Jacobi identity is given by

$$\alpha_1 \left\{ P_{p+3}([e_{q+1}, e_n] + [e_{q+2}, e_{n-1}]) - P_{q+r+2}([e_{n-2}, e_n]) - \right. \\ \left. P_{p+3}([e_{q+2}, e_{n-1}] + [e_{q+1}, e_{n-2}]) \right\} = \\ \alpha_1 \left\{ P_{p+4}([e_{q+2}, e_n]) - P_{q+r+2}([e_{n-2}, e_n]) - P_{p+4}([e_{q+3}, e_{n-1}]) \right\}.$$

Now, from the recursive definition of the linear maps P_h (see Remark 4) and Vandermonde's identity for combinatorial numbers, we obtain

$$P_{n-z_2+1}([e_{z_1+k}, e_{n-k}]) = \binom{q+1}{k} \alpha_1.$$

Consequently,

$$P_{p+4}([e_{q+2}, e_n]) = \binom{p+2}{r-z_2+1} \alpha_1 \\ P_{q+r+2}([e_{n-2}, e_n]) = \binom{q+r}{r-1} \alpha_1 \\ P_{p+4}([e_{q+3}, e_{n-1}]) = \binom{p+2}{r-z_2+2} \alpha_1.$$

We conclude that the coefficient of e_{p+4} in the Jacobi identity is given by

$$\alpha_1^2 \left\{ \binom{p+2}{r-z_2+1} - \binom{q+r}{r-1} - \binom{p+2}{r-z_2+2} \right\} = \\ \alpha_1^2 \left\{ -\frac{z_1-2}{q+1} \binom{p+2}{q} - \binom{q+r}{r-1} \right\}.$$

The previous expression is zero if and only if $\alpha_1 = 0$.

□

Notation 4. We recall here the expressions introduced in Notation 3 and introduce some more useful notations

$$a_m = \binom{m+q-1}{m} \binom{m+p}{q} - \binom{m+q}{m} \binom{m+p}{q-1} - \binom{p+m}{m} \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} R_k, \\ b_m = \binom{m+q-1}{m} \binom{m+p}{q+1} - \binom{m+q-1}{m-1} \binom{m+p}{q} - \binom{m+q}{m} \binom{m+p}{q} \\ - \binom{m+q}{m-1} \binom{m+p}{q-1} - \binom{m+p}{m-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} R_k - \binom{m+p}{m} \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} S_k, \\ c_m = \binom{m+q-1}{m-1} \binom{m+p}{q+1} - \binom{m+q}{m-1} \binom{m+p}{q} - \binom{m+p}{m-1} \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} S_k.$$

Lemma 3. *Let \mathfrak{g} be a n -dimensional non-model filiform Lie algebra associated with the triple (z_1, z_2, n) , whose derived algebra $\mathcal{D}\mathfrak{g}$ is not abelian. Then, for $m = 0, \dots, r-1$, the coefficient of the vector e_{m+p+2} in the Jacobi identity $J(e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-1}, e_n) = 0$ is*

$$a_m \gamma_1^2 + b_m \gamma_1 \alpha_2 + c_m \alpha_2^2.$$

Proof. First, from Lemma 2, we can suppose that $\alpha_1 = 0$ in Theorem 2. Next, by using that theorem, Remark 4 and Vandermonde's identity for combinatorial numbers, we obtain the following relation

$$P_{n-z_2}([e_{z_1+k}, e_{n-k}]) = \binom{q}{k} \gamma_1 + \binom{q}{k-1} \alpha_2. \quad (5)$$

Now, let us consider the Jacobi identity

$$J(e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-1}, e_n) = [[e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-1}], e_n] + [[e_{n-1}, e_n], e_{z_1+m}] + [[e_n, e_{z_1+m}], e_{n-1}] = 0.$$

Notice first that from Theorem 2 we have

$$[e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-1}] = \sum_{h=2}^{m+q} P_h([e_{z_1+m-1}, e_{n-1}] + [e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-2}])e_{h+1} + \beta_{m, n-z_2-1} e_2$$

and then

$$\begin{aligned} [[e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-1}], e_n] &= \sum_{h=2}^{m+q} P_h([e_{z_1+m-1}, e_{n-1}] + [e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-2}])[e_{h+1}, e_n] + \beta_{m, n-z_2-1} [e_2, e_n] \\ &= \sum_{h=z_1-1}^{m+q} P_h([e_{z_1+m-1}, e_{n-1}] + [e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-2}])[e_{h+1}, e_n]. \end{aligned}$$

Next, for the second term, we have

$$[e_{n-1}, e_n] = \sum_{h=2}^{q+r+1} P_h([e_{n-2}, e_n])e_{h+1} + \beta_{n-z_1-1, n-z_2} e_2,$$

so

$$\begin{aligned} [e_{z_1+m}, [e_{n-1}, e_n]] &= \sum_{h=2}^{q+r+1} P_h([e_{n-2}, e_n])[e_{z_1+m}, e_{h+1}] + \beta_{n-z_1-1, n-z_2} [e_{z_1+m}, e_2] \\ &= \sum_{h=z_1}^{q+r+1} P_h([e_{n-2}, e_n])[e_{z_1+m}, e_{h+1}]. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, for the last term, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} [e_{z_1+m}, e_n] &= \sum_{h=2}^{m+q+1} P_h([e_{z_1+m-1}, e_n] + [e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-1}])e_{h+1} + \beta_{m, n-z_2} e_2 \\ [[e_{z_1+m}, e_n], e_{n-1}] &= \sum_{h=2}^{m+q+1} P_h([e_{z_1+m-1}, e_n] + [e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-1}])[e_{h+1}, e_{n-1}] + \beta_{m, n-z_2} [e_2, e_{n-1}] \end{aligned}$$

$$= \sum_{h=z_1-1}^{m+q+1} P_h([e_{z_1+m-1}, e_n] + [e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-1}]][e_{h+1}, e_{n-1}].$$

Consequently, Jacobi identity $J(e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-1}, e_n) = 0$ is equivalent to

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{h=z_1-1}^{m+q} P_h([e_{z_1+m-1}, e_{n-1}] + [e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-2}]][e_{h+1}, e_n] - \sum_{h=z_1}^{q+r+1} P_h([e_{n-2}, e_n])[e_{z_1+m}, e_{h+1}] \\ & - \sum_{h=z_1-1}^{m+q+1} P_h([e_{z_1+m-1}, e_n] + [e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-1}]][e_{h+1}, e_{n-1}] = 0. \end{aligned}$$

According to equality (5), we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} P_{m+q+1}([e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-1}]) &= \binom{m+q-1}{m} \gamma_1 + \binom{m+q-1}{m-1} \alpha_2 \\ P_{m+p+2}([e_{m+q+1}, e_n]) &= \binom{m+p}{q} \gamma_1 + \binom{m+p}{q+1} \alpha_2 \\ P_{m+q+2}([e_{z_1+m}, e_n]) &= \binom{m+q}{m} \gamma_1 + \binom{m+q}{m-1} \alpha_2 \\ P_{m+p+2}([e_{m+q+2}, e_{n-1}]) &= \binom{m+p}{q-1} \gamma_1 + \binom{m+p}{q} \alpha_2. \end{aligned}$$

Next, by using equality (5) and combinatorics, it is easy to prove that

$$P_{q+r+1}([e_{n-2}, e_n]) = \gamma_1 \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} R_k + \alpha_2 \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} S_k$$

and

$$P_{m+p+2}([e_{z_1+m}, e_{q+r+2}]) = \binom{m+p}{m} \gamma_1 + \binom{p+m}{m-1} \alpha_2.$$

Consequently, the coefficient of e_{m+p+2} in the first term of the Jacobi identity is given by

$$\left\{ \binom{m+q-1}{m} \gamma_1 + \binom{m+q-1}{m-1} \alpha_2 \right\} \left\{ \binom{m+p}{q} \gamma_1 + \binom{m+p}{q+1} \alpha_2 \right\},$$

while the coefficient of e_{m+p+2} in the second term is

$$-\left\{ \gamma_1 \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} R_k + \alpha_2 \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} S_k \right\} \left\{ \binom{m+p}{m} \gamma_1 + \binom{m+p}{m-1} \alpha_2 \right\}$$

and the coefficient of e_{m+p+2} in the third term is

$$-\left\{ \binom{m+q}{m} \gamma_1 + \binom{m+q}{m-1} \alpha_2 \right\} \left\{ \binom{m+p}{q-1} \gamma_1 + \binom{m+p}{q} \alpha_2 \right\}.$$

Therefore, the coefficient of e_{m+p+2} in the Jacobi identity $J(e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-1}, e_n) = 0$ is as follows

$$\begin{aligned} & \left\{ \binom{m+q-1}{m} \gamma_1 + \binom{m+q-1}{m-1} \alpha_2 \right\} \left\{ \binom{m+p}{q} \gamma_1 + \binom{m+p}{q+1} \alpha_2 \right\} \\ & - \left\{ \gamma_1 \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} R_k + \alpha_2 \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} S_k \right\} \left\{ \binom{m+p}{m} \gamma_1 + \binom{m+p}{m-1} \alpha_2 \right\} \\ & - \left\{ \binom{m+q}{m} \gamma_1 + \binom{m+q}{m-1} \alpha_2 \right\} \left\{ \binom{m+p}{q-1} \gamma_1 + \binom{m+p}{q} \alpha_2 \right\} = \\ & a_m \gamma_1^2 + b_m \gamma_1 \alpha_2 + c_m \alpha_2^2. \end{aligned}$$

□

Notation 5. Recall that we have denoted by $\mathcal{F}_{\alpha\beta\gamma}$ the family of filiform Lie algebras with associated triple (z_1, z_2, n) , see Notation 2. We denote by $\mathcal{F}_{\alpha\gamma}$ the intersection of $\mathcal{F}_{\alpha\beta\gamma}$ with the linear subspace defined by the equations $\beta_{k\ell} = \gamma_{k+\ell-1}$ if $k + \ell \leq n - z_2$. In [13, Table 1], there is a description of the family $\mathcal{F}_{\alpha\gamma}$ up to dimension 14.

Lemma 4. Let \mathfrak{g} be a n -dimensional non-model filiform Lie algebra belonging to the family $\mathcal{F}_{\alpha\gamma}$ and associated with the triple (z_1, z_2, n) , whose derived algebra $\mathcal{D}\mathfrak{g}$ is not abelian and satisfying $\gamma_i = \alpha_{i+1} = 0$, for $i = 1, \dots, k-1$. Then, for $m = 0, \dots, r-1$, the coefficient of the vector $e_{m+p+4-2k}$ in the Jacobi identity $J(e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-1}, e_n) = 0$ is

$$a_m \gamma_k^2 + b_m \gamma_k \alpha_{k+1} + c_m \alpha_{k+1}^2$$

where a_m, b_m and c_m where defined in Notation 4.

Proof. Similar to the proof of Lemma 3

□

Theorem 3. Any n -dimensional filiform Lie algebra in the family $\mathcal{F}_{\alpha\gamma}$ has derived length 3.

Proof. Let \mathfrak{g} be a Lie algebra belonging to the family $\mathcal{F}_{\alpha\gamma}$ with associated triple (z_1, z_2, n) . If $z_2 = n - 1$, then \mathfrak{g} is metabelian according to Remark 1. In case that $z_2 = n - 2$, Lemma 1 implies that \mathfrak{g} has derived length 3.

We assume now that \mathfrak{g} is a non-model filiform Lie algebra with $z_2 \leq n - 3$. In that case, $n \geq 8$ due to inequalities (4) and the derived Lie algebra $\mathcal{D}\mathfrak{g}$ is not abelian. According to Lemma 2, we can assume that $\alpha_1 = 0$ in the law given in Theorem 2. Therefore, in $\mathcal{D}^2\mathfrak{g}$ we have the following three types of brackets

$$[e_{z_1+i}, e_{z_2+1}] = \alpha_2 e_{i+1} + \dots + \alpha_{i+1} e_2 \quad \text{for } 0 \leq i \leq z_2 - z_1;$$

$$[e_{z_1}, e_{z_2+j}] = \gamma_1 e_j + \dots + \gamma_{j-1} e_2 \quad \text{for } 2 \leq j \leq n - z_2 - 1;$$

$[e_{z_1+k}, e_{z_2+\ell}] = \sum_{h=2}^{k+\ell} P_h([e_{z_1+k-1}, e_{z_2+\ell}] + [e_{z_1+k}, e_{z_2+\ell-1}])e_{h+1} + \gamma_{k+\ell-1} e_2$ for $2 \leq \ell \leq n - z_2 - 1$, and $0 < k < z_2 - z_1 + \ell$.

Consequently, $D^2\mathfrak{g}$ is contained in the greatest of the following spaces

$$\langle e_2, \dots, e_{z_2-z_1+2} \rangle, \quad \langle e_2, \dots, e_{n-z_2} \rangle, \quad \langle e_2, \dots, e_{2n-z_1-z_2-2} \rangle.$$

Notice that $z_2 - z_1 + 2 \leq 2n - z_1 - z_2 - 2$ since $z_2 \leq n - 3$. Moreover, $n - z_2 \leq 2n - z_1 - z_2 - 2$ due to the fact that $n - z_1 \leq n - z_2 \leq 2$.

Therefore, $D^2\mathfrak{g} \subset \langle e_2, \dots, e_{2n-z_1-z_2-2} \rangle$. Let us notice that if $2n - z_1 - z_2 - 2 < z_2 + 1$, then $D^3\mathfrak{g} = \{0\}$ by definition of z_2 , that is, when $z_1 > 2(n - z_2) - 4$ we can affirm that \mathfrak{g} has derived length 3.

Now, we suppose that $4 \leq z_1 \leq 2(n - z_2) - 4$ where $z_2 \leq n - 3$ and verifying expression (4). We are going to prove that there is no filiform Lie algebra associated with the triple (z_1, z_2, n) under these conditions.

In order to do so, we consider the Jacobi identities $J(e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-1}, e_n) = 0$, for $0 \leq m \leq n - z_1 - 2$ and we prove, inductively, that, at least, one of the two following brackets is zero

$$[e_{z_1}, e_n] = \gamma_1 e_{n-z_2} + \gamma_2 e_{n-z_2-1} + \dots + \gamma_{n-z_2-1} e_2,$$

$$[e_{z_2}, e_{z_2+1}] = \alpha_2 e_{z_2-z_1+1} + \dots + \alpha_{z_2-z_1+1} e_2$$

which is a contradiction with the definition of the invariants z_1 and z_2 .

First, we consider the equations defined by the coefficient of e_{m+p+2} in the Jacobi identities $J(e_{z_1}, e_{n-1}, e_n) = 0$ and $J(e_{z_1+1}, e_{n-1}, e_n) = 0$. Notice that those expressions were obtained in Lemma 3 and are given by

$$\gamma_1^2 a_0 + \gamma_1 \alpha_2 b_0 = 0 \tag{6}$$

$$\gamma_1^2 a_1 + \gamma_1 \alpha_2 b_1 + \alpha_2^2 c_1 = 0, \tag{7}$$

where

$$a_0 = \binom{p}{q} - \binom{p}{q-1} - \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} R_k = \frac{(p-2q+1)}{(p-q+1)} \binom{p}{q} - \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} R_k$$

$$b_0 = \binom{p}{q+1} - \binom{p}{q} - \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} S_k = \frac{(p-2q-1)}{(q+1)} \binom{p}{q} - \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} S_k$$

$$a_1 = q \binom{p+1}{q} - (q+1) \binom{p+1}{q-1} - (p+1) \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} R_k = \frac{(p-2q+1)}{(p-q+2)} q \binom{p+1}{q} - (p+1) \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} R_k$$

$$b_1 = q \binom{p+1}{q+1} - \binom{p+1}{q} - (q+1) \binom{p+1}{q} - \binom{p+1}{q-1} - \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} R_k - (p+1) \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} S_k =$$

$$\frac{(q(p-2q-2)-2)(p-q+2)-q(q+1)}{(q+1)(p-q+2)} \binom{p+1}{q} - \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} R_k - (p+1) \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} S_k$$

$$c_1 = \binom{p+1}{q+1} - \binom{p+1}{q} - \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} S_k = \frac{p-2q}{p-q+1} \binom{p+1}{q+1} - \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} S_k$$

Now, we compute the difference between the equation (6) multiplied by $(p+1)$ and equation (7), obtaining

$$\gamma_1^2 a' + \gamma_1 \alpha_2 b' - \alpha_2^2 c_1 = 0, \quad (8)$$

where

$$a' = \frac{(p-2q+1)(p-2q+2)}{p-q+2} \binom{p+1}{q}$$

and

$$b' = \frac{(p-q+2)\{(p-2q)^2 + (q+1)\} + q(q+1)}{(p-q+2)(q+1)} \binom{p+1}{q} + \sum_{k=0}^{\lfloor \frac{r}{2} \rfloor} R_k$$

Let us consider the equation system formed by equations (6) and (8). Notice that if $\gamma_1 = 0$, then we conclude that $\alpha_2 = 0$ since $c_1 \neq 0$. Analogously, if $\gamma_2 = 0$, then we obtain that $\gamma_1 = 0$ due to the fact that $a_0 \neq 0$. Consequently, we suppose that $\gamma_1 \neq 0$ and $\alpha_2 \neq 0$. From equation (6), we obtain

$$\gamma_1 = -\frac{b_0}{a_0} \alpha_2$$

Now, we substitute in equation (8), obtaining

$$\alpha_2^2 \left(\frac{b_0^2 a'}{a_0^2} - \frac{b_0 b'}{a_0} - c_1 \right) = 0$$

Therefore, we obtain the expression

$$b_0^2 a' = a_0(a_0 c_1 - b_0 b') \quad (9)$$

Next, we analyze the sign of the constants a_0, b_0, a', b', c_1 . By using the definition of p, q, r and expression (4), it is easy to prove that

$$a_0 < 0, \quad b_0 < 0, \quad a' \geq 0, \quad b' > 0, \quad c_1 < 0$$

Let us notice that in both cases, we obtain a contradiction with expression (9). We conclude that

$$\gamma_1 = \alpha_2 = 0$$

Next, for the inductive step, we assume that $\gamma_k = \alpha_{k+1} = 0, \forall 1 < k < \ell$, where $\ell = \min\{n - z_2 - 1, z_2 - z_1\}$. Now, we impose the coefficient of $e_{m+p+4-2\ell}$ in the Jacobi identity $J(e_{z_1+m}, e_{n-1}, e_n) = 0$, for $m = \ell - 1$ and $m = \ell$, to be zero. Let us notice that those coefficient were obtained in Lemma 4. Following a similar reasoning, we can conclude that

$$\gamma_\ell = \alpha_{\ell+1} = 0$$

Consequently, we obtain that $[e_{z_1}, e_n] = 0$ and/or $[e_{z_2}, e_{z_2+1}] = 0$ and this is a contradiction with the definition of invariants z_1 and z_2 , see Subsection 2.1.

□

Remark 5. Notice that we have proved in particular that if (z_1, z_2, n) satisfies

$$4 \leq z_1 \leq 2(n - z_2) - 4 \quad \text{and} \quad z_1 \leq z_2 \leq n - 3 \leq 2z_2 - 5,$$

then $\mathcal{F}_{\alpha\beta\gamma}$ is the empty set. The number of triples (z_1, z_2, n) in the previous region is asymptotically $\frac{n^2}{3}$.

Remark 6. In [8, Example 3.2] an example of a filiform Lie algebra with dimension 15 and derived length 4 was given. Using Theorem 2 we can generalize this example providing a family of 15-dimensional filiform Lie algebras with derived length 4 associated with the triple $(4, 9, 15)$. This family is given by the following law:

$$\begin{aligned} [e_1, e_h] &= e_{h-1} \text{ for } 3 \leq h \leq 15, & [e_4, e_{15}] &= \gamma_5 e_2, \\ [e_6, e_{15}] &= (\gamma_5 + 2\beta_{1,5} + \beta_{2,4})e_4, & [e_6, e_{13}] &= \beta_{2,4}e_2, \\ [e_7, e_{13}] &= (\beta_{2,4} + \beta_{3,3})e_3, & [e_5, e_{14}] &= \beta_{1,5}e_2, \\ [e_7, e_{15}] &= (\gamma_5 + 3\beta_{1,5} + 3\beta_{2,4} + \beta_{3,3})e_5, & [e_5, e_{15}] &= (\gamma_5 + \beta_{1,5})e_3, \\ [e_8, e_{13}] &= (\beta_{2,4} + 2\beta_{3,3} + \beta_{4,2})e_4, & [e_6, e_{14}] &= (\beta_{1,5} + \beta_{2,4})e_3, \\ [e_8, e_{14}] &= (\beta_{1,5} + 3\beta_{2,4} + 3\beta_{3,3} + \beta_{4,2})e_5, & [e_7, e_{12}] &= \beta_{3,3}e_2, \\ [e_8, e_{15}] &= (\gamma_5 + 4\beta_{1,5} + 6\beta_{2,4} + 4\beta_{3,3} + \beta_{4,2})e_6, & [e_7, e_{14}] &= (\beta_{1,5} + 2\beta_{2,4} + \beta_{3,3})e_4, \\ [e_9, e_{12}] &= (\beta_{3,3} + 2\beta_{4,2} + \alpha_6)e_4, & [e_8, e_{11}] &= \beta_{4,2}e_2, \\ [e_9, e_{13}] &= (\beta_{2,4} + 3\beta_{3,3} + 3\beta_{4,2} + \alpha_6)e_5, & [e_8, e_{12}] &= (\beta_{3,3} + \beta_{4,2})e_3, \\ [e_9, e_{14}] &= (\beta_{1,5} + 4\beta_{2,4} + 6\beta_{3,3} + 4\beta_{4,2} + \alpha_6)e_6, & [e_9, e_{10}] &= \alpha_6 e_2, \\ [e_9, e_{15}] &= (\gamma_5 + 5\beta_{1,5} + 10\beta_{2,4} + 10\beta_{3,3} + 5\beta_{4,2} + \alpha_6)e_7, & [e_9, e_{11}] &= (\beta_{4,2} + \alpha_6)e_3, \\ [e_{10}, e_{12}] &= (\beta_{3,3} + 3\beta_{4,2} + 2\alpha_6)e_5, & [e_{10}, e_{11}] &= (\beta_{4,2} + \alpha_6)e_4, \\ [e_{10}, e_{13}] &= (\beta_{2,4} + 4\beta_{3,3} + 6\beta_{4,2} + 3\alpha_6)e_6, & & \\ [e_{10}, e_{14}] &= (\beta_{1,5} + 5\beta_{2,4} + 10\beta_{3,3} + 10\beta_{4,2} + 4\alpha_6)e_7, & & \\ [e_{10}, e_{15}] &= \gamma_5 + 6\beta_{1,5} + 15\beta_{2,4} + 20\beta_{3,3} + 15\beta_{4,2} + 5\alpha_6)e_8, & & \\ [e_{11}, e_{12}] &= (\beta_{3,3} + 3\beta_{4,2} + 2\alpha_6)e_6, & & \\ [e_{11}, e_{13}] &= (\beta_{2,4} + 5\beta_{3,3} + 9\beta_{4,2} + 5\alpha_6)e_7, & & \\ [e_{11}, e_{14}] &= (\beta_{1,5} + 6\beta_{2,4} + 15\beta_{3,3} + 19\beta_{4,2} + 9\alpha_6)e_8, & & \\ [e_{11}, e_{15}] &= (\gamma_5 + 7\beta_{1,5} + 21\beta_{2,4} + 35\beta_{3,3} + 34\beta_{4,2} + 14\alpha_6)e_9, & & \\ [e_{12}, e_{13}] &= (\beta_{2,4} + 5\beta_{3,3} + 9\beta_{4,2} + 5\alpha_6)e_8, & & \\ [e_{12}, e_{14}] &= (\beta_{1,5} + 7\beta_{2,4} + 20\beta_{3,3} + 28\beta_{4,2} + 14\alpha_6)e_9, & & \\ [e_{12}, e_{15}] &= (\gamma_5 + 8\beta_{1,5} + 28\beta_{2,4} + 55\beta_{3,3} + 62\beta_{4,2} + 28\alpha_6)e_{10}, & & \\ [e_{13}, e_{14}] &= (\beta_{1,5} + 7\beta_{2,4} + 20\beta_{3,3} + 28\beta_{4,2} + 14\alpha_6)e_{10}, & & \\ [e_{13}, e_{15}] &= (\gamma_5 + 9\beta_{1,5} + 35\beta_{2,4} + 75\beta_{3,3} + 90\beta_{4,2} + 42\alpha_6)e_{11}, & & \\ [e_{14}, e_{15}] &= (\gamma_5 + 9\beta_{1,5} + 35\beta_{2,4} + 75\beta_{3,3} + 90\beta_{4,2} + 42\alpha_6)e_{12}. & & \end{aligned}$$

verifying the following relations

$$\alpha_6 = \frac{1}{14}\beta_{3,3}, \quad \gamma_5 = 363\beta_{3,3}, \quad \beta_{1,5} = 27\beta_{3,3}, \quad \beta_{2,4} = \frac{21}{5}\beta_{3,3}, \quad \beta_{4,2} = \frac{3}{10}\beta_{3,3}$$

Notice that [8, Example 3.2] is obtained for $\beta_{3,3} = \frac{1}{858}$.

Finally, it is also possible to give a general family of filiform Lie algebras with dimension 31 and derived length 5. This family is associated with the triple $(4, 17, 31)$ whose law is obtained with these 14 parameters

$$\begin{aligned} &\alpha_{14}, \quad \gamma_{13}, \quad \beta_{1,13}, \quad \beta_{2,12}, \quad \beta_{3,11}, \quad \beta_{4,10}, \quad \beta_{5,9}, \\ &\beta_{6,8}, \quad \beta_{7,7}, \quad \beta_{8,6}, \quad \beta_{9,5}, \quad \beta_{10,4}, \quad \beta_{11,3}, \quad \beta_{12,2} \end{aligned}$$

and the derived series of this algebra \mathfrak{g} is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}^0 \mathfrak{g} &= \mathfrak{g}, \quad \mathcal{D} \mathfrak{g} = \langle e_2, \dots, e_{30} \rangle, \quad \mathcal{D}^2 \mathfrak{g} = \langle e_2, \dots, e_{26} \rangle, \quad \mathcal{D}^3 \mathfrak{g} = \langle e_2, \dots, e_{18} \rangle, \\ \mathcal{D}^4 \mathfrak{g} &= \langle e_2 \rangle, \quad \mathcal{D}^5 \mathfrak{g} = \{0\}. \end{aligned}$$

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